

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF NON-LINEAR ORTHOTROPIC POROUS-DUCTILE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY. Effective properties of non-linear, elastoplastic two-phase composites are here studied in the particular case of a vacuum inclusion embedded in a ductile metal matrix. The constitutive behaviour of the porous-ductile medium is described by means of an instantaneous yield criterion, which bounds the elastic domain and is a function of the current microstructural geometry, and by means of evolution laws for the internal state variables that are assumed to characterize the microstructure. In order to derive the homogenized behaviour of the orthotropic two-phase composite, the kinematic approach of limit analysis is applied to a cylindrical Representative Volume Element (RVE) with elliptic cross-section containing a coaxial and confocal elliptic cylindrical cavity. The influence of microstructure evolution on the effective response of the RVE is discussed and compared to the available results, which are based on the transversely isotropic Gurson's model. Attention is limited to loading conditions with principal directions of the stress and strain-rate tensors aligned with the principal axes of the RVE geometry, in order to rule out the effects induced by plastic spin on the material behaviour.

KEYWORDS: effective properties, micromechanics, plasticity, anisotropy, porous media, voids, metal matrix composite.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are usually characterized by two distinct length scales: a microscopic one l_m , which corresponds to the size of the heterogeneity or to the distance among heterogeneities within the homogeneous matrix material, and a macroscopic one l_M , which is characteristic of the specimen geometry and of the scale of variation of the applied loading conditions. Effective properties are aimed at describing the homogenized behaviour of the multi-phase, locally non-homogeneous solid on the basis of the material behaviour of each phase and of the microstructural geometry.

In the present paper it is assumed that the composite possesses a statistically uniform microstructure, so that periodic boundary conditions are not dealt with in the analysis of the single RVE.

Porous-ductile media can be treated as two-phase composites, the first phase being the elastoplastic metal matrix and the second one the cavity which is surrounded by the matrix. In order to obtain the overall (effective, homogenized) constitutive behaviour of

porous-ductile solids, homogenization techniques are required; these procedures must be able to handle the nonlinear behaviour of the matrix and the spatial arrangement of the voids.

The void growth process in non-linear solids has been mainly studied by McClintock [1], Rice & Tracey [2] and Budiansky et al. [3] for single cavities in an infinite medium. Gurson developed his model [4] for a cavity contained in a finite-dimensions RVE. This RVE is not able to fill the continuum without gaps or overlaps because of the geometry of its outer surface; the bounds on the effective strength properties of porous-ductile media have thus to be intended as approximate estimates for the behaviour of the actual homogenized continuum.

Recently, the homogenized behaviour of anisotropic two-phase composites has been extensively studied [5, 6]. Since plastic finite-deformation loadings can largely distort the microstructural geometry, account has to be taken of the microstructure evolution to describe the actual response of porous media under general loading conditions.

In this paper the analyses are carried out for a hollow cylindrical volume characterized by an elliptic cross-section: in order to simplify the computations and to obtain semi-analytical effective mechanical properties, it is assumed that the longitudinal outer RVE boundary and the void-matrix interface are confocal surfaces. Results are obtained under the constraint that the longitudinal RVE axis is a principal direction for the overall stress and strain rate tensors.

What is sought here is an assessment of the effects of the aspect ratio of the void cross-section on the homogenized mechanical properties of porous-ductile solids. In order to pursue this aim the kinematic approach of limit analysis is followed; this allows to obtain the effective yield domain under generalized plane strain conditions.

This study set the bases for the formulation of constitutive models comprised of an instantaneous effective yield condition, which is function of the current microstructure and of the matrix material strength, associated flow rules for the plastic components of the macroscopic strain-rate tensor and evolution laws for the internal state variables that characterize the microstructural geometry.

THEORETICAL BASES

In this Section the approach to the characterization of the overall mechanical properties of porous media introduced by Gurson [4] and applied in the following to orthotropic porous materials is briefly described.

Let us consider a RVE of a two-phase heterogeneous material. In order to evaluate analytically the nonlinear response of the heterogeneous solid, two assumptions are made:

- no velocity discontinuities are allowed within the RVE, so that the strain rate tensor can be defined as the symmetrized gradient of the velocity field: $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = 1/2 (v_{i,j} + v_{j,i})$;
- the continuum equilibrium equations at the boundaries between phases with different mechanical properties are satisfied by the components of tractions.

Once the microstructure has been defined in terms of the volume fraction of each phase, the homogenized properties of the heterogeneous medium need to be expressed in terms of average quantities over the RVE volume V , namely in terms of the macroscopic strain rate \dot{E}_{ij} and stress Σ_{ij} tensors.

The response of the RVE is sought for given uniform strain rates boundary conditions on the outer boundary ∂V of the RVE, that is:

$$v_i(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{E}_{ij}x_j \quad \text{on } \partial V \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

\mathbf{x} being the position vector within the RVE.

The non-linear behaviour of the matrix material is assumed incompressible, rigid perfectly-plastic, with a yield condition $\phi(\sigma_{ij}) = 0$ described by means of J₂-flow theory of plasticity:

$$\phi(\sigma_{ij}) = \sigma_{eq} - \sigma_0 = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}s_{ij}s_{ij}} - \sigma_0, \quad s_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3}\delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where: σ_{ij} and s_{ij} are the stress and the stress deviator tensors, respectively; σ_{eq} is the Mises equivalent stress; σ_{kk} is the stress tensor trace; δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta; σ_0 is the uniaxial strength of the matrix material.

For porous materials the second phase is approximated as a cavity with stress-free boundary; due to the isochoric property of the matrix, the dilatant behaviour of the RVE is linked to the evolution of the void volume V_v .

Let the macroscopic plastic dissipation be defined according to:

$$\dot{W} \equiv \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} dV = \frac{1}{V} \int_{\Omega} \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} dV = \frac{\sigma_0}{V} \int_{\Omega} \dot{\epsilon}_{eq} dV, \quad (3)$$

where the integration is taken over the volume Ω of the rigid ideally-plastic matrix due to the null strength properties of the void. In the above Eqn. (3) the local plastic dissipation is the doubly contracted product of the microscopic stress and strain rate tensors.

It can be proven that the macroscopic stress at yielding can be obtained as [4, 7]:

$$\Sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_{ij}}. \quad (4)$$

The effective yield function thus inherits the properties of convexity and associativity of the local one for the matrix material.

An estimate of the effective yield function can be derived from an approximate velocity field, linear in \dot{E}_{ij} , within the matrix material: this estimate can be shown to possess the properties of convexity and normality possessed by the actual one [4]. It can also be proven that the approximate yield domain always lies on or outside the actual one.

EFFECTIVE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ORTHOTROPIC POROUS-DUCTILE MEDIA

An orthotropic constitutive model for porous-ductile solids is presented in this Section. Aim of this model is to take into account the microstructural anisotropy induced by the shape and spatial arrangement of the voids as well as by plastic straining during external loading.

The microstructural geometry is characterized by a cylindrical RVE with an elliptic cross-section, containing a coaxial and confocal elliptic cylindrical cavity (see Fig. 1). The anisotropy in the cross-section plane is described by the parameter c , defined as:

$$c \equiv \frac{a^2 - b^2}{4}, \quad (5)$$

where a and b are the semiaxes lengths aligned with the reference axes x_2 and x_1 , respectively. From (5) it follows that: $c > 0$ when the ellipse is as in Fig. (1a) with the major axis along x_2 ; $c = 0$ when the ellipse reduces to a circle; $c < 0$ when the ellipse has its

Figure 1. *Representative Volume Element cross-section geometry*

major axis along x_1 (Fig. (1b)).

The internal state variables that define the orthotropic microstructure are the void volume fraction f and the aspect ratio λ of the void in the RVE cross-section. The porosity f is defined as the ratio between the volume V_v of the cavity and the RVE volume V (see Fig. (1)), while the aspect ratio λ is defined as the ratio between the ellipse axes lengths aligned with axes x_2 and x_1 on the cavity surface:

$$f = \frac{V_v}{V} = \frac{a_1 b_1}{a_2 b_2}, \quad \lambda = \frac{a_1}{b_1}. \quad (6)$$

Approximate upper bound on the effective yield condition

An orthonormal curvilinear reference frame is introduced, related to the standard cartesian one x_1, x_2, x_3 by means of the following transformation in the RVE transverse cross-section:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = r \left(1 - \frac{c}{r^2}\right) \sin \beta \\ x_2 = r \left(1 + \frac{c}{r^2}\right) \cos \beta \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

A continuous velocity field at plastic collapse, which spreads over the whole matrix volume Ω , is introduced; by means of matrix incompressibility and boundary conditions (1), this velocity field can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} v_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_2 b_2}{r^2 - c} (\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_{33}) + \dot{E}_b - \frac{2a_2}{a_2 + b_2} \dot{E}_{33} \right] x_1 \\ v_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_2 b_2}{r^2 + c} (\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_{33}) - \dot{E}_b - \frac{2b_2}{a_2 + b_2} \dot{E}_{33} \right] x_2 \\ v_3 = \dot{E}_{33} x_3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\dot{E}_a \equiv \dot{E}_{11} + \dot{E}_{22}, \quad \dot{E}_b \equiv 2 \frac{b_2 \dot{E}_{11} - a_2 \dot{E}_{22}}{a_2 + b_2}. \quad (9)$$

More detailed discussions about the effects on the homogenized material properties of the rate of deformation field assumed within the matrix material can be found in [7].

The macroscopic plastic dissipation turns out to be expressed as:

$$\dot{W} = \frac{\sigma_0}{V} \int_{\Omega} \dot{\epsilon}_{eq} d\Omega = \frac{\sigma_0}{\pi L a_2 b_2} \int_0^L dx_3 \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{1}{r^3} dr \int_0^{2\pi} H \dot{\epsilon}_{eq}(r, \beta) d\beta, \quad (10)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}$ is the equivalent microscopic strain rate field deduced from the velocity field (8) and $H/r^3 \equiv (r^4 + c^2 - 2cr^2 \cos 2\beta)/r^3$ is the absolute value of the Jacobian of the transformation $(x_1, x_2) \rightarrow (r, \beta)$. The integration in Eqn. (10) is carried out over the volume Ω of the matrix: $\Omega \equiv \{(r, \beta, x_3) : r_1 \leq r \leq r_2, 0 \leq \beta \leq 2\pi, 0 \leq x_3 \leq L\}$.

Following the same procedure which has led to the closed-form pressure dependent Guron's yield condition for circular cylindrical RVE [4], a Taylor series expansion of the equivalent microscopic strain rate field of Eqn. (10) in terms of $\cos(2\beta)$ is performed around $\cos(2\beta) = 0$. This expansion, if arrested at the first order, gives rise to:

$$\dot{W} = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{3}\pi a_2 b_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{1}{r^3} dr \int_0^{2\pi} H \dot{\epsilon}_{eq}(r, \beta) d\beta \cong \frac{2\sigma_0}{\sqrt{3}a_2 b_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{r^4 + c^2}{r^3} \sqrt{\dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I} dr, \quad (11)$$

being:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I \equiv & \dot{E}_b^2 + 4 \left(1 - \frac{a_2 b_2}{(a_2 + b_2)^2} \right) \dot{E}_{33}^2 + 2 \frac{b_2 - a_2}{b_2 + a_2} \dot{E}_b \dot{E}_{33} \\ & + \frac{a_2 b_2}{r^4 + c^2} \left(\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_{33} \right) \left[-2c \left(\dot{E}_b + \frac{b_2 - a_2}{b_2 + a_2} \dot{E}_{33} \right) + a_2 b_2 \left(\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_{33} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

The upper bound on the effective yield domain, here expressed in terms of macroscopic stress components conjugate to the macroscopic strain rates \dot{E}_a , \dot{E}_b and \dot{E}_{33} , can thus be obtained as:

$$\Sigma_a = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_a} = \frac{2\sigma_0}{\sqrt{3}a_2 b_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{r^4 + c^2}{r^3} \frac{\dot{\Theta}_{eqa}^I}{2\sqrt{\dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I}} dr, \quad (12a)$$

$$\Sigma_b = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_b} = \frac{2\sigma_0}{\sqrt{3}a_2 b_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{r^4 + c^2}{r^3} \frac{\dot{\Theta}_{eqb}^I}{2\sqrt{\dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I}} dr, \quad (12b)$$

$$\Sigma_{33} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_{33}} = \frac{2\sigma_0}{\sqrt{3}a_2 b_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{r^4 + c^2}{r^3} \frac{\dot{\Theta}_{eq33}^I}{2\sqrt{\dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I}} dr, \quad (12c)$$

where $\dot{\Theta}_{eqa}^I$, $\dot{\Theta}_{eqb}^I$, and $\dot{\Theta}_{eq33}^I$ are the derivatives of $\dot{\Theta}_{eq}^I$ with respect to \dot{E}_a , \dot{E}_b and \dot{E}_{33} , respectively.

The components of the Σ_{ij} tensor at yielding aligned with the axes of the ellipses in the RVE transverse cross-section are computed according to (see Eqns. (9)):

$$\Sigma_{11} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_{11}} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_a} \frac{\partial \dot{E}_a}{\partial \dot{E}_{11}} + \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_b} \frac{\partial \dot{E}_b}{\partial \dot{E}_{11}} = \Sigma_a + \frac{2b_2}{a_2 + b_2} \Sigma_b, \quad (13a)$$

$$\Sigma_{22} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_{22}} = \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_a} \frac{\partial \dot{E}_a}{\partial \dot{E}_{22}} + \frac{\partial \dot{W}}{\partial \dot{E}_b} \frac{\partial \dot{E}_b}{\partial \dot{E}_{22}} = \Sigma_a - \frac{2a_2}{a_2 + b_2} \Sigma_b, \quad (13b)$$

where use has been made of the chain rule for differentiation.

Eqns. (12), not integrable in closed-form, can be expressed in terms of elliptic integrals

Figure 2. *Projections onto the $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{33}$ (a), $\Sigma_{22} - \Sigma_{33}$ (b) and $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{22}$ (c) planes of the effective yield condition ($f = 0.05, \lambda = 1$)*

of the first and second kind. Topics related to the numerical integration of Eqns. (12) are not further explained here for brevity; they will be treated in details in a forthcoming paper, where numerical finite-step time integration algorithms will be developed.

The approximation (12) constitutes an upper bound on the actual solution of the problem. The degree of accuracy with respect to the exact solution is reduced by the simplifications introduced in order to obtain the semi-analytical homogenized plastic behaviour of porous-ductile solids: the higher the values of f and λ the worst the accuracy of the numerical solution (see [7]).

As far as three-dimensional loading conditions are concerned, at fixed value of porosity $f = 0.05$ the effective yield locus is shown in Figs. (2) and (3) for eccentricities $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 30$, respectively. These yield domains are represented in terms of projections onto the $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{33}$, $\Sigma_{22} - \Sigma_{33}$ and $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{22}$ macroscopic stress planes. The aspect ratio λ acts in these plots by progressively reducing the dimensions of the effective yield surface: a noteworthy reduction of the effective yield domain with respect to the transversely isotropic Gurson's model represented by Fig. (2), accompanied by a rotation of the line through the poles of the domain, is evidenced in Fig. (3). The major reduction in the homogenized strength properties of the elliptic cylindrical RVE is displayed in these figures along the reference axis x_1 , that is along the minor principal axis of the elliptic void cross-section.

From the above figures it can be concluded that both the porosity f and the void aspect

Figure 3. *Projections onto the $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{33}$ (a), $\Sigma_{22} - \Sigma_{33}$ (b) and $\Sigma_{11} - \Sigma_{22}$ (c) planes of the effective yield condition ($f = 0.05, \lambda = 30$)*

ratio λ act as *softening* parameters.

Evolution laws for the microstructure

The anisotropy described by this model can be due to the shape of the inclusions at the beginning of the deformation process, as generated during metal forming processes like, e.g., rolling, or can be induced by plastic straining for initially transversely isotropic inclusion shapes and spatial distributions. In such cases the orientation of the inclusions is not randomly distributed; the isotropy or transverse isotropy is thus lost and privileged material directions must be taken into account.

By neglecting the effects of induced anisotropy during the loading process the material strength is overestimated, as it can be seen from the smaller dimensions of the effective yield domains represented in Figs. (2) and (3) at higher values of λ for a fixed value of porosity f .

For principal directions of the macroscopic strain rate and stress tensors aligned with the axes of the cartesian reference frame, namely with the privileged directions of the RVE geometry, the microstructure is defined by means of void volume fraction f and void aspect ratio λ ; the void orientation with respect to a fixed global reference frame is assumed constant throughout the whole deformation process.

It can be shown that the velocity field (8) allows the void to evolve maintaining an elliptic cross-section. The variation of the semiaxes lengths aligned with axes x_1 and x_2 gives

rise to the following evolution laws for the porosity f and the void aspect ratio λ , where account has been taken of the matrix incompressibility:

$$\dot{f} = (1 - f) \frac{\dot{V}_v}{V} = (1 - f) [\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_{33}], \quad (14a)$$

$$\dot{\lambda} = \left(\frac{a_1}{b_1} \right) \dot{b}_1 = \frac{1}{b_1^2} (\dot{a}_1 b_1 - a_1 \dot{b}_1) = \frac{\lambda}{f} \frac{1 - \lambda}{1 + \lambda} \dot{E}_a - \lambda \dot{E}_b + \left(\frac{\lambda}{f} \frac{1 - \lambda}{1 + \lambda} - \lambda \frac{1 - \kappa_v}{1 + \kappa_v} \right) \dot{E}_{33}, \quad (14b)$$

being:

$$\kappa_v \equiv \left(\frac{fV}{2} \frac{\lambda^2 - 1}{\lambda} \right) + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{fV}{2} \frac{\lambda^2 - 1}{\lambda} \right)^2}.$$

In what precedes it has been assumed that the RVE geometry is characterized by two confocal ellipses, which are the void-matrix interface and the outer RVE boundary. Nevertheless, the velocity field (8) causes the two ellipses to have different foci at the end of the deformation rate process. This means that an approximation is introduced in the model, which is necessary in order to obtain the analytical results here developed.

NON-LINEAR RESPONSE OF ORTHOTROPIC POROUS-DUCTILE SOLIDS

Aim of this Section is to study the influence of the microstructural anisotropy in the $x_1 - x_2$ plane (in the void cross-section) and of the microstructure evolution on the material behaviour, under the assumption of small strain fields.

Results are presented for radial loading paths in the $\varepsilon_{11} - \varepsilon_{22}$ strain plane, namely at fixed values of $\kappa_\varepsilon \equiv \varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_{11}$. In what follows the tensors ε_{ij} and σ_{ij} represent the elastoplastic homogenized behaviour of the porous material. Lowercase greek symbols denote now the nonlinear response at the material level. The numerical finite-step time integration is obtained by means of the explicit second order Runge-Kutta algorithm: details related to this topic will be treated in a forthcoming paper.

Matrix material is here characterized by the following elastic and strength properties: $E/\sigma_{0y} = 400$, E being the Young modulus and σ_{0y} the initial flow stress; Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.3$; strain hardening exponent $n = 5$. An initial porosity $f_0 = 0.05$ is assumed throughout.

To assess the influence of the void aspect ratio on the behaviour of the porous solid, two initial values of λ (say λ_0) in the unstressed configuration have been considered: $\lambda_0 = 1$ and $\lambda_0 = 3$. The case $\lambda_0 = 1$ corresponds to an initially transversely isotropic behaviour and constitutes the reference to appraise the effects of the aspect ratio on the softening regime of the material behaviour; $\lambda_0 = 3$ gives rise to results for moderately orthotropic microstructural geometry.

In Figs. (4) and (5) results are compared with the corresponding ones obtained by preventing the void aspect ratio to vary (denoted by $\lambda = 1.0 = \text{const.}$ and $\lambda = 3.0 = \text{const.}$). Under plane strain conditions, only biaxial strain states that induce reduction of the void aspect ratio are treated. By allowing λ to vary, results display a reduction of the softening instead of a further increase of it: this is due to the opposite interacting effects of void growth and aspect ratio decrease.

Results are presented in Figs. (4) and (5) in terms of stress-strain relationships along the x_1 and x_2 reference axes and in terms of variations of porosity and void aspect ratio.

Figure 4. *Effects of λ on the nonlinear response of porous-ductile materials at $\kappa_\varepsilon \equiv \varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_{11} = -0.5$ with $f_0 = 0.05$. (a) σ_{11} vs ε_{11} ; (b) σ_{22} vs ε_{22} ; (c) sketch of the strain state; (d) f vs ε_{11} ; (e) λ vs ε_{11}*

An interesting feature of the behaviour of moderately orthotropic materials can be seen in Figs. (4a-b): for $\lambda_0 = 3$ a softening branch is displayed by the $\sigma_{22} - \varepsilon_{22}$ relationship, while the $\sigma_{11} - \varepsilon_{11}$ relation shows a sort of perfect plasticity-like behaviour. These figures show that, by allowing λ to vary, softening effects are always reduced during plastic loading. On the other hand, void growth is never affected much by the variation of the void aspect ratio.

From the above results it can be seen that the nonlinear behaviour of porous solids during plastic loading can be better understood by means of this micromechanics-based orthotropic constitutive model. The effects shown in these figures can be further increased if finite strains are taken into account. During ductile crack growth, in the process zone ahead of the crack tip a better description of the phenomenon of void growth to coalescence, governed by intense finite strains, can thus be based on this enhanced micromechanics based analysis of the void-containing continuum.

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Figure 5. Effects of λ on the nonlinear response of porous-ductile materials at $\kappa_\epsilon \equiv \epsilon_{22}/\epsilon_{11} = 0.0$ with $f_0 = 0.05$. (a) σ_{11} vs ϵ_{11} ; (b) σ_{22} vs ϵ_{22} ; (c) sketch of the strain state; (d) f vs ϵ_{11} ; (e) λ vs ϵ_{11}

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